

ANDES, the high-resolution spectrograph for ELT: the AO system

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ABSTRACT

ANDES (ArmazoNes High Dispersion Echelle Spectrograph) is the high-resolution spectrograph under development for the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT). It is designed to operate in both seeing-limited and adaptive optics (AO) modes, covering a spectral range of 0.4 to 1.8 μm with a resolving power of approximately 100,000.

A critical component of ANDES is the Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) system, which provides AO correction for the Integral Field Unit (IFU) feeding the YJH spectrograph. The primary scientific goal of the SCAO-IFU system is to characterize exoplanet atmospheres through high-contrast observations in reflected light. This will be achieved by combining high-contrast imaging and high-dispersion spectroscopy to observe exoplanets with a contrast down to 10^{-7} . To this end, the SCAO system aims to provide star point spread function (PSF) with high Strehl ratios and great contrast before IFU injection. Specifically, the SCAO system aims for a raw contrast of 10^{-3} at 20–30 mas for a star with $I=8$ magnitude at 1600nm. To reach this level of contrast, the SCAO WFS uses a modulated pyramid sensor, assisted by a petalometer in the NIR to enable the M4 differential piston control and includes a coronagraphic unit that can be inserted or removed from the optical path, as needed.

The subsystem PDR of the SCAO was successfully passed in February 2025 and now the SCAO subsystem is preparing to address the ANDES system PDR planned for summer 2026. This work presents the PDR design of the ANDES SCAO subsystem, where fine control of M4 petalling error enables achieving a SR of approximately 80% at 1600nm in bright regime under median seeing conditions. The contrast delivered to the IFU will improve by roughly 1 order of magnitude thanks to a deployable coronagraphic unit. For fainter reference stars, the SCAO is estimated to deliver ~60% SR at 1600 nm with $I=14$ (median seeing), with dedicated strategies to push performance toward even fainter targets.

Keywords: ANDES, Adaptive Optics, Coronagraph, exoplanets, contrast,

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1. INTRODUCTION

The ArmazoNes high Dispersion Echelle Spectrograph (ANDES) marks a major advancement in astronomical instrumentation and is being developed to operate on the European Southern Observatory's Extremely Large Telescope (ELT). With its enormous 39-meter primary mirror, the ELT is set to become the most powerful optical and near-infrared telescope ever built, offering observing capabilities far beyond those of existing facilities. Within this framework, ANDES is conceived as a high-resolution spectrograph that will exploit the ELT's exceptional light-gathering capacity to tackle some of the most profound questions in contemporary astrophysics.

Designed^[1] to provide high precision of wavelength calibration (< 1 m/s, goal: 0.1 m/m) and an high resolution ($R \sim 100.000$), ANDES will cover an extensive wavelength range, from 0.4 μm in the visible to 1.8 μm in the near-infrared, with planned extensions pushing the limits even further, from 0.37 μm to 2.4 μm . Such broad spectral access is essential for a wide variety of scientific investigations, including detailed examinations of exoplanet atmospheres, chemical and physical studies of distant galaxies, and precise measurements related to the expansion history of the universe.

The main scientific drivers^[2] of ANDES are:

1. **Identifying potential biosignatures in exoplanet atmospheres through transmission spectroscopy:** By studying starlight that filters through an exoplanet's atmosphere, ANDES can search for molecular fingerprints associated with biological activity.
2. **Searching for possible changes in fundamental physical constants:** Ultra-precise spectroscopic observations of remote quasars and other distant sources may reveal whether constants of nature have evolved over cosmological timescales.
3. **Exoplanets analysis using reflection spectroscopy:** By analyzing the light reflected from an exoplanet's surface or atmosphere, ANDES offers complementary insights to those obtained through transmission spectroscopy.
4. **Measuring cosmic acceleration directly via the Sandage effect:** Long-term, extremely high-precision monitoring of galaxy redshifts could reveal their minute time-dependent variations, providing a direct measurement of the universe's expansion rate.

To achieve these scientific goals, ANDES adopts a modular, fiber-fed, cross-dispersed echelle spectrograph architecture and operates in two observing configurations: a seeing-limited mode and an IFU mode that is assisted by the Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics system. The schematic view of the functional architecture of ANDES is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Schematic view of functional architecture of overall ANDES instrument. Wavelength coverage is reported in microns.

When ANDES operates in IFU mode, the SCAO dichroic is introduced into the optical beam by the Front End^[3]. This element reflects wavelengths shorter than 980 nm toward the SCAO wavefront sensor (WFS), while transmitting about 90% of the longer wavelengths to the science path.

The IFU^[4] is capable of de-rotating the science field and can observe off-axis targets up to 3 arcsec from the optical axis. It feeds the fiber bundle using four selectable spaxel scales - 7, 16, 35, and 100 mas - providing fields of view with diameters ranging from 44 to 880 mas.

The SCAO WFS^[5] itself operates strictly on-axis and has an acquisition field of view of 10 arcsec in diameter. A coronagraphic module can be inserted into the optical path between the SCAO dichroic and the IFU.

2. CONTROL STRATEGY

The detection and characterization of faint sources which are angularly close to very bright stars requires a diffraction-limited PSF of the ELT that will be delivered by the SCAO module, high-contrast techniques like coronagraphy, and high-dispersion ($R \sim 100,000$) spectroscopy (HDS) that will be provided by the ANDES spectrograph at YJH. One of the most ambitious science goals of ANDES is the detection and characterization of rocky exoplanets in reflected light at angular separations of only a few λ/D . A prime example is Proxima Centauri^[6], whose planet exhibits a contrast of $\sim 10^{-7}$ at separations between 16 and 30 mas.

In theory, HDS can provide a contrast gain of 10^{-4} , which in turn sets the requirement that high-contrast imaging (HCI), when combined with SCAO, must reach a contrast level of 10^{-3} . So, the SCAO sub-system is required to deliver a raw contrast of 3.0×10^{-3} as baseline (with a goal of 1.0×10^{-3}) at the IFU input focal plane. This contrast level must be achieved at a separation of 20 mas from the PSF peak of the AO reference star and across the 1000–1700 nm spectral range. The requirement assumes median seeing conditions and an AO reference star of magnitude $I \leq 8$.

To reach the required high-contrast performance, it is essential to accurately correct the atmospheric turbulence, as well as the static and dynamic aberrations from the telescope and the optical relay. In particular, at the ELT, one of the most challenging types of aberration is the differential piston between the M4 petals. The gaps between the mirror segments, together with the shadows produced by the telescope’s supporting spiders, create obscured regions in the pupil. When these shadowed areas exceed the typical Fried parameter, the wavefront sensor may fail to detect phase discontinuities across the segments. If left uncorrected, this effect can significantly degrade the adaptive optics system’s performance, even under otherwise optimal observing conditions. Moreover, local turbulence in the telescope dome may produce phase jumps between pupil regions, as seen at the VLT with the so-called Low-Wind Effect^[17].

Figure 2. SCAO system control strategies.

To handle these fragmentation errors and the intense telescope dynamics—such as the massive tip-tilt windshake introduced by the ELT’s M2 mirror, which can reach 11 μm RMS—the SCAO system adopts two distinct control strategies (see Figure 2):

- **Low WFE Regime (Bright Star & Good/Median Seeing):** The primary AO WFS Channel performs fast corrections using a pyramid wavefront sensor, compensating for both continuous modes and piston modes across the full pupil (with 4000 global KL modes and no edge-actuator slaving). To mitigate the M2 windshake, the control loop implements a simple/leaky integrator coupled with an Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filter specifically for Tip-Tilt. However, the pyramid WFS is subject to a 2π ambiguity risk. To prevent this, a dedicated Phasing Channel operates at a low frequency (1 Hz) in the infrared (J-H band) to verify the presence of a stable white fringe and measure both LWE-induced and control-induced petals. Under median seeing conditions (0.9 arcsec) and with a bright reference star ($I = 8$), segment jumps occur approximately once every 30 seconds. The Phasing Channel provides a $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ capture range, ensuring reliable piston correction of the M4 petals.
- **High WFE Regime (Faint Star & Poor Seeing):** When seeing exceeds 1.0 arcsec or the reference star is faint ($I > 14$), wavefront residuals compromise the phasing signal. Under these conditions, the system switches to a HARMONI-like strategy using an edge-actuator coupling modal basis^[18]. While not optimal for extreme high-contrast fine phasing, tying the commands of the M4 actuators at the petal edges avoids piston drifts and preserves the coherence of the PSF. Furthermore, for faint targets, the system exploits a cascading control loop with the ELT Prefocal Station (PFS) located at 5 arcmin. The PFS provides fast tip-

tilt correction at a bandwidth of approximately 50 Hz, while the ANDES pyramid WFS dictates the working point at a lower bandwidth of roughly 5 Hz (see Figure 3).

Furthermore, dedicated efforts are underway to accurately identify and estimate specific M4 petal modes that may arise due to the non-orthogonality between differential piston and continuous atmospheric aberrations. Recent work by Rossi et al. (2025)^[19] explores various estimators, including analytical methods and neural network-based approaches, to reliably disentangle these sharp phase discontinuities from the atmospheric turbulence.

Figure 3. Faint star regime PSF at 1600nm. Left, $I = 15$ guide star, center and right, $I = 18$ guide star. Right panel consider a cascading control loop with the ELT Prefocal Station.

3. DESIGN

A schematic representation of the SCAO subsystem is shown in Figure 4. The dichroic splits the incoming beam, sending the reflected light to both the AO WFS channel and the Phasing Channel, while the transmitted light feeds the IFU subsystem. A coronagraphic unit can be inserted into the transmitted optical path between the dichroic and the IFU. The ELT-M4 mirror serves as the adaptive optics corrector, while the real-time control is handled by the Herzberg Extensible Adaptive optics Real-time Toolkit (HEART). Its architecture supports all required functionalities, including temporal control, pyramid optical-gain compensation, modal-gain optimization, and real-time updates of the reconstruction matrix during operations. This latter operation is required because the adopted Front-End architecture does not include any field derotation upstream of the SCAO WFS. As a result, the pupil rotation seen by the WFS is limited to the telescope's elevation tracking. The residual rotation is then compensated numerically by updating the reconstruction matrix during operation, eliminating the need for an optical derotator within the system.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the ANDES-SCAO system and its main components. Green links represent the real-time data connections, the yellow one the optical one the left and the purple are standard data links.

3.1 RTC

The SCAO system will be driven by a high-performance real-time controller (RTC) based on the Herzberg Extensible Adaptive Real-time Toolkit (HEART)^{[7],[8]}. HEART is a collection of libraries and tools specifically developed to implement adaptive-optics real-time systems. With appropriate customization, it can support a wide range of AO architectures, including Single Conjugate AO (SCAO), Ground Layer AO (GLAO), Multi-Object AO (MOAO), and multi-conjugate AO (MCAO). HEART provides a high-speed, low-latency processing pipeline capable of handling pixel streams from the available wavefront sensors in real time, generating commands for the configured wavefront correctors, and offloading selected control signals to telescope mechanisms.

Figure 5. ANDES RTC Context Diagram.

Figure 5 shows the top-level context diagram of the ANDES HERT-based SCAO RTC. The SCAO real-time control system is organized into two tightly interconnected processing domains: Hard Real-Time and Soft Real-Time. The Hard Real-Time section handles all latency-critical operations, receiving pixel streams directly from the Pyramid WaveFront Sensor and communicating with the deformable mirrors through the ELT's deterministic control network, Central Control System (CCS). The Soft Real-Time domain, implemented using the ELT RTC Toolkit, is responsible for computational tasks that are less time-critical but essential for overall system performance. This includes generating control matrices, republishing telemetry, processing the gain-scheduling camera data, and forwarding petalometer measurements to the Hard Real-Time loop.

3.2 SCAO WFS

The adaptive optics system is a single conjugated configuration using a natural guide star. The selected AO wavefront sensor is a modulated pyramid, chosen for its superior sensitivity and reduced aliasing compared with a Shack–Hartmann sensor when operating on a 39-meter aperture. The modulated pyramid WFS is designed with 100 sub-apertures across the telescope pupil and a 120-pixel center-to-center pupil separation, providing a slight spatial oversampling relative to the M4 actuator pitch while maintaining compatibility with cameras equipped with E2V CCD220 detectors (240×240 pixels). This pupil configuration supports binning modes of 2×2 , 3×3 , and 4×4 . The WFS operates over a 600–980 nm wavelength range and has a field of view optimized to ± 1.0 arcsec. Additionally, the system incorporates a gain-scoring camera used to monitor and compensate the pyramid optical gain during operation, enabling stable performance across varying observing conditions.

3.3 Phasing Channel

The SCAO Phasing Channel is designed to ensure accurate phase alignment (working in synergy with the AO WFS) across the segmented mirrors, a key requirement for achieving the precision and contrast needed for high-resolution spectroscopy. The current baseline configuration employs a double-wavelength Linearized Focal-Plane Technique (LIFT)^{[9][10]}, implemented through a dedicated wedge-dichroic that deflects the two bandwidths at different angles onto the phasing detector. The baseline phasing wavefront sensor operating in two narrow infrared bands, 1100–1190 nm and 1210–1300 nm, respectively. The system supports a maximum framerate of 1 Hz, a capture range of at least $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$, and provides differential piston accuracy better than 300 nm.

A prototyping activity for the phasing channel is planned for early Phase C, leveraging the existing facilities at the Arcetri Observatory.

3.4 Coronagraph

The SCAO subsystem incorporates a classical Lyot coronagraph^[11], which is deployed downstream of the SCAO module to enable high-contrast observations in the near-infrared. The optical design is optimized to operate over the 950–1800 nm wavelength range, with an extended goal of reaching 2400 nm, and provides a ± 5 arcsec field of view while ensuring sufficient throughput to preserve the flux from faint planetary companions. The coronagraph features a dual-arm architecture: one arm implements the coronagraphic path used for high-contrast suppression of stellar light, the other, the Camera Arm, is dedicated to the measurement of non-common-path aberrations (NCPA). For the Camera Arm, the adopted solution is to employ a Zernike WFS by inserting a dedicated phase-shifting mask in place of the focal

plane mask (FPM) and imaging the pupil onto the WFS camera. The NCPA correction is then applied as an offset to the SCAO pyramid WFS. These measurements are performed in a narrow spectral band selected by the dichroic, a wavelength range that is not relevant for the science data but adequate for accurate NCPA retrieval.

Mechanically, the subsystem consists of a fixed structure attached to the Front-End structure and a movable structure that translates vertically to insert or retract the coronagraph from the optical path. When deployed, the coronagraph is positioned between the SCAO output and the IFU entrance.

Figure 6. 3D optical layout of the ANDES Coronagraph (left) and Coronagraph in the UP operation position and down position (right)

4. PERFORMANCE

4.1 AO E2E simulations

End-to-end (E2E) simulations of the SCAO system have been carried out using PASSATA^[12], an object-oriented adaptive-optics simulation framework based on IDL and developed at Arcetri Observatory. More recently, these simulations have also been performed using SPECULA^[20], the Python-based successor to PASSATA. This tool has been extensively employed to model a wide range of AO systems - including those of LBT^[13], GMT^[14], and ERIS^[15] - and has been validated on sky, providing a reliable platform for ELT-class simulations. E2E simulations refer to full optical propagation starting from the atmospheric wavefront, passing through the telescope and all associated perturbations, and continuing through the instrument and into the AO control loop. The final output of these simulations is the wavefront at the focal plane.

The current simulation set includes several ELT-specific error terms, such as M1 and M2 wind-shake, pupil shadowing and diffraction from the segmented ELT aperture, and static aberrations of M1. However, some contributors are still missing and will be incorporated in future iterations, including uncorrected non-common-path aberrations

(NCPA) and optical imperfections within the WFS path. For this reason, all results presented at this stage must be regarded as preliminary, pending the integration of the remaining error terms and the consolidation of the full SCAO error budget.

The E2E simulations focused on evaluating system performance in term of contrast and Strehl Ratio across the magnitude range defined for the instrument ($m(I_{AB}) = 6-15$ mag). The following table summarizes the adaptive optics performance as a function of guide-star magnitude and wavelength. For each configuration, the achieved raw contrast and the corresponding Strehl Ratio in the H band are listed. These results consider median seeing condition and zenith angle = 30°.

Table 1. AO contrast at a 20 ± 5 mas distance from the center of the PSF and SR performance.

Magnitude (I-band)	Strehl Ratio (H-band)	$\lambda = 1035$ nm	$\lambda = 1236$ nm	$\lambda = 1614$ nm	$\lambda = 2200$ nm
I = 8	77%	1.37×10^{-3}	1.48×10^{-3}	1.34×10^{-2}	2.90×10^{-2}
I = 12	72%	1.54×10^{-3}	1.56×10^{-3}	1.38×10^{-2}	2.93×10^{-2}
I = 14	60%	2.88×10^{-3}	2.85×10^{-3}	1.50×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}
I = 15	45% (@9.3 mas)	-	-	-	-

Figure 7. AO contrast curves at 1600 nm. The contrast is intended to be computed on the radial profile of the PSF intensity normalized to the peak and averaged over a radial bin of 5mas (first one centered on the peak). All curves are obtained under median seeing conditions using an AO reference star I = 8. Green curve represent the diffraction limited reference case, while the blue and orange curves illustrate the performance achieved at different AO close-loop frequencies. The yellow box highlights the 5 mas radial binnig used in the contrast estimation.

The Figure 7 shows the contrast curve at a wavelength of 1600 nm under median-seeing conditions, using an I=8 natural guide star. The achieved contrast does not yet meet the requirement of 3.0×10^{-3} at 20 mas. To gain one order of magnitude in performance and reach the required contrast level at this separation, a starlight-suppression stage is introduced downstream of the SCAO system. The selected solution is the Classical Lyot Coronagraph presented in

section 3.4, which provides the necessary attenuation of stellar flux to enable high-contrast observations in this regime (see section 4.2).

4.2 AO and Coro simulations

Figure 8 displays the simulated PSF and coronagraphic images in monochromatic light at five different wavelengths ranging between 950 and 1850 nm in median observing condition (JQM) with the coronagraph optimization in YJH band. At a given wavelength, an attenuation of the intensity level is clearly observed from the AO corrected PSF to the coronagraphic image. The structure of the coronagraphic images reveal a combination of two predominant effects: (i) the speckles due to the atmospheric residuals left after SCAO correction and (ii) the diffraction residuals due to the coronagraph effect. Since the AO correction improves toward the red end of the spectrum, the AO residual speckles are prevailing at the shortest wavelengths while the diffraction residuals due to the coronagraph represent the main contributor at the largest wavelengths.

Figure 8. Simulated images of an on-axis point source in median observing conditions after SCAO correction. The top and bottom rows display the frames in log scale of the PSFs and the coronagraphic images with a Lyot coronagraph in YJH configuration, in monochromatic light at 5 different wavelengths ranging from 950 to 1850nm. In the bottom row, the dashed disk represents the projected area of the coronagraph focal plane mask in the final image plane.

This analysis^[11] of the images is confirmed by observing the azimuthally averaged intensity profiles of the PSFs and coronagraphic images at different wavelengths within the considered spectral range and in median seeing conditions, see Figure 9. The profiles of the coronagraphic images shows an intensity level below 10^{-3} at 20 mas from the star, at all the wavelengths shorter than 1800nm, showing the ability of the Lyot coronagraph to achieve the required contrast in YJH bands under JQM.

Figure 9. Left: Azimuthally averaged intensity profiles of the images in JQM after SCAO correction in monochromatic light at different wavelengths. The dashed and solid lines represent the profiles of the PSFs and the coronagraphic images with a Lyot coronagraph optimized in YJH band. The grey area denotes the projected area of the coronagraph focal plane mask in the final image plane. Right: Azimuthally averaged contrast level of the coronagraphic image over an annulus of 5 mas centered at 20mas as a function of the wavelength λ in median conditions. The dashed-line curve represents the contrast with atmospheric residuals and in the absence of the coronagraph. The dot-line curve represents the contrast with no atmospheric residuals and in the presence of the coronagraph. For the curves with AO residuals and coronagraph, the contrast remains below 10^{-3} over the YJH band.

4.3 E2E simulation with APU

To simulate realistic observations with ANDES, an end-to-end simulator called APU (ANDES Performance Unfolded)^[16] is under development. This tool reproduces all steps from high-contrast image generation, photometric and noise modeling, to the injection of astrophysical scenes and final data analysis. APU was applied to a science case involving young Jupiters detected via direct imaging.

Figure 10. The different steps of the end-to-end simulator APU are shown. Using the adaptive-optics simulations as input to compute the high-contrast images, the stellar and planetary spectra are injected. After the estimation of the photometry and the error budget, the light is injected into the fibers. The final step applies the molecular-mapping technique for exoplanet detection and characterization.

4.3.1 Structure and functioning of the APU simulator

A schematic overview of the APU E2E simulator is reported in Figure 10. The simulator comprises different steps: 1/ the PSF or coronagraphic image computation, 2/the planet injection, 3/the simulation of the data processing using the molecular mapping for exoplanet detection and characterisation.

1. The computation of the PSF and coronagraphic images follows the methodology described in Sections 4.1 and 4.2. To simulate a 1-minute exposure, 2,500 instantaneous frames are averaged to produce a single long-exposure image. Repeating this process results in a cube of 120 long-exposure images for each wavelength point in the ANDES grid, corresponding to a total simulated exposure time of approximately 2 hours. In SCAO-IFU mode, the ANDES instrument will operate with three detectors observing simultaneously in the Y, J, and H bands, covering a wavelength range from 0.95 to 1.8 μm at a constant spectral resolving power of $R = 100,000$. This wavelength coverage corresponds to 63,909 spectral samples. For each wavelength channel, images are spatially well sampled on a 150×150 grid, suitable for designing the IFU hexagonal geometry. The resulting datasets consist of three-dimensional cubes of $150 \times 150 \times 63,909$ elements, generated under different seeing conditions (JQ1, JQ2, JQM). This leads to extremely large data volumes and requires substantial computational effort.
2. In this stage of the simulation, the high-contrast images produced previously are used as input. The purpose of the photometry module is to perform realistic photometric measurements on the scientific frames, incorporate synthetic planetary companions into the dataset, and subsequently introduce the various noise sources associated with the detection process. Stellar photometry is based on BT-Dusty PHOENIX models, while the planetary spectra are sourced from the PHOENIX models, specifically the BT-Settl models. Atmospheric absorption and emission at high spectral resolution are simulated using the ESO SkyCalc tool. Thermal emission from both the telescope and the instrument is also included through SkyCalc, whereas the telescope transmission is based on documentation provided by ESO and, for the fibers, by the ANDES consortium.
3. To represent the IFU spaxels, the POPPY package was used to generate a model of 61 hexagonal spatial elements projected onto a highly sampled field of view of 150×150 pixels. For each spaxel, the flux was obtained by integrating all pixel values within the corresponding hexagonal region, assuming a homogeneous light distribution inside each fiber. The noise estimation relies on the ANDES Exposure Time Calculator (ETC), currently developed only for the seeing-limited mode. Background observations are also simulated. Modal noise has not yet been included in the current implementation, and cross-talk effects between adjacent fibers are likewise not modeled. At this stage, the simulator is optimized for on-axis observations, with off-axis capabilities planned for integration in future versions. As a final step, the molecular mapping technique is applied. This technique involves two main operations: (i) subtracting the stellar spectrum by exploiting both the spatial and spectral information available, and (ii) computing the cross-correlation function (CCF) at every location within the field of view.

4.3.2 Science case: study of directly imaged young Jupiters

We present three cases of young Jupiter-like exoplanets orbiting a similar host star, differing only in the spectral type of the injected planetary signal. The three planetary types are selected to represent emblematic directly imaged exoplanets: 51 Eri b, AF Leporis b, and β Pictoris b. In this preliminary analysis, each planet is injected at an angular separation of 30 mas from the host star. Two atmospheric conditions, JQ1 and JQ are explored and the result are shown in Figure 11. The detection limit, fixed at a 5σ threshold, is reached at delta magnitude of $\Delta H \approx 17$ mag for L-type planets (β Pic b) and around $\Delta H \approx 18$ mag for LT-type (AF Lep b) and T-type planets (51 Eri b). These results are highly encouraging for the ANDES performance goals, as the instrument achieves a detectable ΔH magnitude close to 18 which corresponds to the level required for observing Proxima b in reflected light.

Figure 11. S/N as a function of planetary contrast expressed in dmag for the three exoplanet types considered. Each planet was injected at a separation of 30 mas from the host star and perfectly centered onto a spaxel.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work we have presented the requirements that guided the design of the SCAO subsystem and described how the system has been implemented in preparation for the ANDES System PDR. We then reported the current SCAO performance results, highlighting the need to introduce a coronagraph downstream of the adaptive-optics module in order to reach the contrast levels required for detecting the desired scientific targets in reflected-light spectroscopy. Finally, a first end-to-end simulation of the full IFU-mode chain has provided a clear indication of the ANDES detection limits in terms of Δ -magnitude necessary to achieve the host-star-to-exoplanet contrasts of interest. These initial simulation results, however, rely on several simplifying assumptions and therefore require further consolidation through extended simulation campaigns and a more comprehensive error-budget assessment.

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